

Religion (Pentecostalism) As A Social Cultural Institution

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MEDIA AND SOCIAL CULTURAL INSTITUTIONS

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Introduction

Society has many facets to it. There are many institutions embedded within a society that form and determine how individuals react to the environments in which they live. Religion is one institution which is very important in most societies around the world.

Religion is both a belief system and a social institution. As a belief system, religion shapes what people think and how they see the world. As a social institution, religion is a pattern of social action organized around the beliefs and practices that people develop to answer questions about the meaning of existence. As an institution, religion persists over time and has an

organizational structure into which members are socialized. (<http://sociology.about.com>).

Usually, people pass their faith and religion through generations as part of their culture such that if one is born a Muslim, chances are that he or she will retain that faith and pass it on to the children in the same way that it was passed to him or her by the parents or guardians. Religion therefore carries within it very deeply held beliefs and values that are not easily changed. But religion is also adaptable. It adapts within the cultural environment that it is nurtured in. It is influenced by either existing institutions, and it also equally influences them. It adapts to the environment in which a particular faith is practiced.

There are many different religions in the world today. But the dominant ones are Christianity and Islam, of which both have a significant following in the world today. Statistics indicate that presently, Christianity has about 2.1 billion followers, making about 33% of the world population, followed by Islam, which has around 1.5 billion followers, about 21% of the world population.

The effect of this cannot be ignored and the presence of these faiths are felt everywhere. Religion has many definitions. Geertz (1973) defined religion as “a cultural system of symbols which acts to establish powerful, pervasive and long lasting moods and motivations in men, by formulating conceptions with such aura of factuality, that the moods and motivations seem uniquely realistic” (Geertz 1973, p. 90). Therefore, religion has to do with a people’s beliefs and perceptions. Religion is also a belief in a supernatural being that is beyond all humanity, who is all powerful.

Modern day Christianity has grown over the years, and spread since the days of Christ and His disciples. It has also grown to have different aspects of it such as the traditional church, the charismatic's who believe in the Holy Spirit and His gifts to men and how these gifts are manifested in the world.

The paper discusses two Pentecostal preachers, one in Kenya, a pastor Wanderi, of the Christian Fellowship Foundation, CFF in Kiambu. The other pastor that the paper discusses is Joel Osteen, an American preacher based in Texas, United States. The two represent modern charismatic preachers both in Kenya and America. The paper is based on watching a number of their programs, both on television and using online media such as you-tube.

This paper examines the themes of their messages, and some of the persuasive techniques that they employ, as well taking note of the media channels that they use to get across to their audiences.

Theoretical background

For purposes of discussing this paper, the writer will apply three communication theories. These are; framing theory, elaboration likelihood theory and the narratives paradigm as applied in a persuasive communication context.

Framing

This is closely related to the agenda setting theory, concept of framing. Scheufele (1999) notes that not only are agenda setting and framing theories related, but insists that framing may indeed be an extension of agenda setting theory (p.104). Additionally, he notes that "framing is

embedded in the larger context of media effects research” (ibid, p. 104). Further, he emphasizes that framing assumes that how an issue is characterized in news reports influences how audiences understand that particular issue. Baran & Davis (2006, p. 282) also point out to the fact that in frame analysis, there is a specific set of expectations which is used to make sense of a social situation at a given point in time. It is the media that highlights the issue or frames it for the audience. Once the issue is framed, it begins to become significant for that particular audience. According to Gitlin (1980) he defines frames as “principles of selection, emphasis and presentation composed of little tacit theories about what exists, what happens, and what matters” (p.6). Frames guide how an issue is perceived and how reality is presented. Framing is done in such a manner such that an audience is presented with information in such a manner as to view and understand it in that way. This may not be consciously done on the part of the source or the audience but either way, the effects are the same since the audience will still assimilate that information in a particular manner. But the effects of framing is that it causes the audience to interpret their reality from a particular vantage point because this is what is noticed and becomes real in the eyes of the audience. They therefore will pay attention to these particular issues that have been framed.

How does this apply to religion as a social cultural institution?

Modern day preachers and Christians have not been left behind in their usage of the media. In many ways, Christians have been affected by the proliferation of media and media technologies just like other people in society. Many preachers are making use of both traditional media as well as new media to propagate the Gospel. Both traditional Christian churches and Pentecostals appear to be outdoing each other in their use of media. However, the Pentecostals appear to be

more visible. They seem to lead their congregations in a new definition of who God is and how to define the Christian faith. This is in form of the frames that they present to their audiences.

Christianity is no longer perceived as a boring faith, but one that is vibrant and trendy. Christians are rich upwardly mobile, technologically, savvy prosperous etc. This makes the faith seem more appealing and relevant to their audiences. Even the way God is presented, is no longer one to be feared, but He is more of a friend or a buddy, not a consuming fire.

Life is looked at from a more positive dimension, emphasis of heaven and hell is less. Rather, living well while down here on earth, is encouraged. One can desire to be a Christian in order to become like the preachers, or to be what the preachers promise in their sermons.

Limitations

In compiling this paper, the writer faced the challenge in that though the data was gotten from television, constraints of time would not allow. Therefore, there was the use of internet such as YouTube, to access some of the sermons. In addition, the Kenyan pastor, i.e. Wanderi did not have his sermons on you tube or other media except television; the writer could only rely on a single sermon from television, though followed him on the social sites.

Methodology

The writer watched sermons presented by Pastor Wanderi, on GBS Television, and Pastor Osteen on Family Television. Since the sermons were only a few episodes, the writer still watched more on you-tube.

The questions that the writer asked were:

- i) What themes to these Pentecostal preachers pass about the Christian faith to their congregations?
- ii) What are some of the persuasive strategies applied in their preaching?

Pastor Wanderi

Based in a growing church in Kiambu town, this pastor represents an emerging group of Kenyan pastors, who minister mainly to either upper or lower middleclass people. The particular message preached had to do with God's authority and why Christians need to take this authority and use it and apply it in their own day to day lives. In this sermon aired on Tuesday the 4th in one of the Christian channels, the pastor used several real life experience stories, humor and even emotional appeals, to drive his message home.

The themes in his message range from how to use God given authority, how to stop being poor, to deal with difficult situations, to be positive, and to escape suffering. Watching his audience closely, and based on their occasional verbal responses, one could see that the audience easily identified with the message and it seemed to resonate in their own lives.

Joel Osteen

He is a well known American preacher, in the United States who heads a mega-church that he has build over time, after taking over from his father. His is a well known church with

many followers. Being a modern charismatic preacher, his style is different from other traditional preachers and mainstream churches.

Pastor Osteen uses modern media and technology such as television, the internet, to reach his very large audiences. He brings out modernity, charm and positivity of the modern Christian faith. He uses many stories and anecdotes to illustrate his points. At the beginning of each sermon, he asks his congregants to recite very specific lines concerning the Bible. This serves as a form of identity with his congregation, helps hold their attention and prepares them for the message.

Some of his strategic persuasive techniques he uses include the use of appeals like humor, emotional appeals, and appeal to logic. The themes carried within his messages include positive thinking, freedom, victory in life, hope, power, faith, God's favor. It is rare that this preacher mentions sin, redemption, etc, which are common themes in the Christian faith traditions.

The writer did watch a number of programs both on television and on you-tube in which the sermons were presented. Some of the titles included;

- Speak faith into your future aired on 1/1/2012
- Staying passionate about life aired on 4/12/ 2011
- You are a no lack person aired on 8/1/2012

Conclusion

Media can be used to change perceptions as well as influence an audience's way of thinking and understanding a phenomenon. When sermons are aired on a particular medium, they are not value free. They too are laden with views and perceptions that bear marks of influence from the source. Religion and in this case, Christianity has not been left behind Modern day Pentecostal preachers are able to use the media not only to persuade, but to influence perceptions and shape frames of reference for their audience.

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